

An Empirical Mid-Latitude Model of the C_kL Irregularity Index from 35 MHz Scintillation Data

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ABSTRACT

This paper summarizes work focused on improving the ability to assess and predict the level of km-scale ionospheric irregularities at mid-latitudes based on a recently developed capability to measure 35 MHz scintillations using cosmic radio sources. The Deployable Low-band Ionosphere and Transient Experiment (DLITE) is a low-cost, interferometric radio telescope optimized for ionospheric remote sensing rather than sensitive astronomical imaging. DLITE uses intensity scintillations of a handful of exceptionally bright cosmic radio sources to characterize the level of km-scale irregularities via the C_kL irregularity index, which is proportional to the vertically integrated electron density variance. DLITE arrays are currently operational in Maryland, New Mexico, and Florida. Here, we describe a spherical harmonic-based model fit to $\log_{10}C_kL$ measurements from these arrays that includes a term for short-term forecasting ($\sim 1\text{--}3$ days). We will show that meter-scale irregularity activity detected with the Blackstone, Virginia SuperDARN radar correlates with C_kL nowcasts/forecasts, indicating that model performs reasonably well.

1 INTRODUCTION

Radio frequency (RF) scintillations due to small-scale irregularities within the ionosphere are a significant issue for systems that utilize transionospheric signal paths or refraction through the ionosphere for over-the-horizon (OTH) propagation. For microwave systems like the Global Positioning System (GPS), this is generally only an issue at high and low latitudes where irregularity activity is relatively high (e.g., Kintner et al., 2007). Activity at mid-latitudes is usually quite low relative to these other regions. However, since the impact grows with the wavelength of the signal, high frequency (HF; 3–30 MHz) and very high frequency (VHF; 30–300 MHz) scintillations are still typically present, even at mid-latitudes. Since there are few if any satellite-based signals of opportunity within these frequency regimes, observationally characterizing scintillation levels at mid-latitudes is challenging.

In part to address this issue, The Deployable Low-band Ionosphere and Transient Experiment (DLITE) was developed. DLITE is a low-cost, interferometric radio telescope consisting of four inverted vee-shaped dipole antennas developed for the Long Wavelength Array (LWA; Taylor et al., 2012) project. Unlike telescopes like the LWA, which are designed to maximize sensitivity for astrophysical investigations, DLITE is optimized for ionospheric remote sensing and affordability/ease of deployment to facilitate widespread geographical coverage. The telescope resolves multiple exceptionally bright cosmic radio sources (2–4 at a time) in a 30–40 MHz band using time and frequency

difference of arrival (TDOA and FDOA, respectively) methods rather than beam forming. This is made possible by separating the antennas by $\sim 200\text{--}500$ m and using a bandwidth of $\sim 8\text{--}10$ MHz. The apparent intensity of each source is monitored to characterize scintillations due to km-scale irregularities (Fresnel scale is $\sim 1\text{--}2$ km). The system and methods developed to convert these scintillation measurements to the frequency- and geometry-independent $C_k L$ irregularity index are described in detail by Helmboldt et al. (2021).

In the autumn of 2019, DLITE arrays were established in southern Maryland near the town of Pomonkey (DLITE-POM) and in New Mexico at the site of the Very Large Array (DLITE-NM). A third array was installed at Malabar Annex Space Force Base in Florida near the end of 2021 (DLITE-FL). Examination of $C_k L$ measurements from DLITE-POM and DLITE-NM over many months revealed that they were well correlated with a delay of ~ 2 hours. This is the expected result if $C_k L$ depends more strongly on local solar time rather than location. Armed with this knowledge and a modest network of three DLITE arrays, an empirical model was developed for $\log_{10} C_k L$ based on spherical harmonics as functions of latitude and local time. An additional term was added to allow the mean $\log_{10} C_k L$ to vary linearly from day-to-day without changing the local time/latitude dependence, which facilitates short-term forecasting ($\sim 1\text{--}3$ days).

This paper describes the construction and testing of this model, including comparisons with the climatological Wideband Model (WBMOD; Fremouw and Secan, 1984) of transionospheric RF scintillations. This is presented in Sec. 2 with conclusions following in Sec. 3.

2 THE EMPIRICAL SCINTILLATION MODEL

2.1 DATA AND METHODS

As described by Helmboldt et al. (2021), using a single pair of antennas, or “baseline,” and image of the sky can be produced with about ~ 1 hour of DLITE data. The primary data products generated by the DLITE system are cross correlations of complex voltages, or “visibilities,” for each of the six unique baselines. These are channelized in frequency across the full band centered at 35 MHz and coherently averaged within a chosen integration time. Nominally, the band is 8.33 MHz wide and the data are initially output with 512 frequency channels and integrated within 1.024-s intervals. After flagging for short-duration and/or narrow-band interference, these are averaged down to 64 channels and an integration time of 60.416 s (59×1.024 s).

A TDOA/FDOA image can then be generated from a subset of the visibilities of each baseline with a simple two-dimension fast Fourier transform (FFT) with the frequency and time axes being the Fourier complements to TDOA and FDOA, respectively. To ensure a well-behaved impulse response, a two-dimensional Hamming window is applied. Each cosmic radio source has a predictable TDOA/FDOA for a particular baseline and time interval and can be easily located within such an image. Intensity variations caused by irregularities create a plateau-like artifact in the FDOA direction only (see Helmboldt et al., 2021; Helmboldt, 2023, for examples). The magnitude of this artifact relative to the measured source intensity provides a means to compute the S_4 index, which can be used in turn to determine $C_k L$ (Rino, 1979; Helmboldt et al., 2021).

Missing data that was flagged due to short-duration interference, however, can produce similar FDOA artifacts. To mitigate this, we developed a method to fill such data gaps for instances where $<25\%$ of the visibility data were flagged. If more data than that were flagged for a particular time interval, it was not used. This method uses a linear combination of the expected cosmic

Figure 1: An example of the spherical harmonic-based empirical model for $\log_{10}C_kL$. The upper two panels show images of the spherical harmonic model as functions of latitude and local time at the beginning and end of the period of time used for the fit, 25–31 Dec. 2021, with measurement locations plotted as cyan dots. The bottom two panels show the measured $\log_{10}C_kL$ values (black dots) with the fitted values (blue dots) as functions of local time and latitude. In these panels, the WBMOD 50th percentile values are also plotted for comparison (red dots).

Figure 2: The same as Fig. 1, but for data from 24–30 Apr. 2022.

source visibilities plus a constant fit to the unflagged visibilities to fill in interference-flagged data. Extensive tests of the application of this method with many months of data from all three DLITE arrays showed that it effectively removed a bias toward higher C_kL for data with larger amounts of flagged data without adding a negative bias (i.e., it did not over correct for this bias).

2.2 MODEL DEVELOPMENT AND TESTS

As mentioned in Sec. 1, several months of data from New Mexico and Maryland indicated that scintillation levels vary more strongly with local time than geographic location. This motivated the construction of a model based on spherical harmonics such that

$$\log_{10}C_kL = \sum_{\ell=0}^2 \sum_{m=-\ell}^{\ell} c_{\ell,m} Y_{\ell}^m(LT \times 15^{\circ}, 90^{\circ} - \varphi) + c_0(d - d_0), \quad (1)$$

where LT is the local time in hours, φ is the latitude, and d is the day number relative to a reference day, d_0 . The $c_{\ell,m}$ and c_0 coefficients are determined via a linear fit using multiple days of data. With this formulation, the shape and amplitude of the local time/latitude dependence are kept fix throughout the time period being fit. However, the mean $\log_{10}C_kL$ per day is allowed to increase/decrease linearly with time via the $c_0(d - d_0)$ term. It is this term that allows for forecasting via extrapolation to future dates in a reasonably well-constrained manner. Equation (1) also allows for a diurnal pattern that varies with latitude due to, e.g., changes in sunset/sunrise times. It should be noted that with a denser network of a larger number of arrays, higher-order spherical harmonic terms could be included. However, with the current three-array network, we set $\ell \leq 2$. Since multiple cosmic radio sources are used to determine C_kL , the latitude and longitude of each measurement are taken from the mean 300-km altitude pierce point location, weighted by source intensity. In practice, inputs for φ are clipped to be between 26° and 43° based on the coverage of the three DLITE arrays.

This process is illustrated with examples in Figs. 1 and 2. In each of these cases, the model was fit to one week of data. The two upper panels in each figure show images of the spherical harmonic representations of $\log_{10}C_kL$ as functions of local time and latitude for the first and last dates of the fitting period. One can see subtle-but-noticeable differences between the images for the two dates due to the $c_0(d - d_0)$ term. The lower panels show the measured values of $\log_{10}C_kL$ in black with the fitted values in blue versus local time in one panel and latitude in the other. One can see that the model does a reasonable job of reproducing the observations. It is also apparent that the latitude/local time dependence changed significantly from Dec. 2021 to Apr. 2022. For comparison, we have also plotted 50th percentile values from WBMOD (v18.02) as red points. The wintertime WBMOD values are nearly all lower than the observed DLITE values with no significant local time variation. The springtime values are comparable to DLITE, but with a different diurnal pattern.

As a partial test of the performance of this model, we have compared $\log_{10}C_kL$ nowcasts and three-day forecasts with the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) of meter-scale irregularities detected with the Blackstone, Virginia station (BKS) of the Super Dual Aurora Radar Network (SuperDARN; Nishitani et al., 2019). Since the radar cross section for such irregularities is proportional to the electron density variance (e.g., Schlegel, 1996), there should be a correlation between irregularity SNR and C_kL . This is not without caveats, however, since C_kL is a measure of the vertically integrated electron density variance and, in this case, is based on 35 MHz data that are sensitive to km-scale rather than meter-scale irregularities. Nevertheless, an observed relationship between the

Figure 3: Distributions of the irregularity backscatter SNR detected with the BKS radar as functions of $\log_{10}C_kL$ taken from (left) the DLITE nowcast model, (middle) the DLITE three-day forecast model, and (right) the WBMOD 50th percentile values. Contours show the percentiles of the SNR distribution within each $\log_{10}C_kL$ bin.

two would provide some level of conformation that the $\log_{10}C_kL$ model is behaving in a reasonable way.

To this end, data were obtained from BKS for the dates of 11 Dec. 2021 through 20 Jun. 2022 when all three DLITE arrays were collecting data. For each radar echo not flagged as ground scatter, $\log_{10}C_kL$ was computed with the DLITE model at the location of the echo using the preceding five days of data for a nowcast and data from eight through three days prior for a three-day forecast. Additionally, the 50th percentile WBMOD value was also computed. For each model, the BKS data were binned by $\log_{10}C_kL$ and within each bin, the 10th, 25th, 50th, 75th, and 90th percentile of the SNR (in dB) distribution was determined. Curves showing these as functions of $\log_{10}C_kL$ are shown in Fig. 3 for each of the three model cases. For both DLITE models, there is a noticeable correlation between BKS SNR and $\log_{10}C_kL$, especially for the higher percentile curves. For the WBMOD case, the relatively narrow range in allowed $\log_{10}C_kL$ values makes it difficult to determine the existence of similar trends, but none are obvious.

3 Conclusions

We have demonstrated an empirical model for irregularity levels at mid-latitude as quantified with the C_kL irregularity parameter. With a modest number of sensors (three) spread throughout the continental United States, we showed that a relatively low-order spherical harmonic fit to the data as a function of latitude and local time yielded a reasonable representation of observed trends in $\log_{10}C_kL$. While not entirely definitive, an observed correlation between $\log_{10}C_kL$ computed with this model in both nowcast and three-day forecast modes with irregularity backscatter SNR from the BKS radar provided an encouraging test of the model’s performance.

While this model is currently limited to the region covered by the three DLITE arrays, the system was designed to be low-cost (materials cost currently ~\$45k) and relocatable. Thus, it is an affordable option for many research and/or academic institutions around the world to enable basic ionospheric research and hands-on learning of RF systems and interferometry for students. As more DLITE telescopes are added to the globe, this model can likewise expand in both coverage and complexity.

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